

Catalytic diazotization using silver and gold nanoparticles and spectrophotometric determination of parathion residues in fruit and soil

Shilpa Sharma^{a*} and Manas Kanti Deb^b

^aRungta Engineering College, Near Nandanvan, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

E-mail : shilpa.creative@gmail.com

^bSchool of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

Manuscript received online 26 December 2012, revised 31 January 2013, accepted 28 March 2013

Abstract : The catalytic activity of silver and gold nanoparticles in the spectrophotometric determination of parathion using 1-naphthol as a new coupling reagent to form an azo dye is described. It is based on the reduction of nitro group in parathion with zinc/HCl to form an amino derivative, which is diazotized and subsequently coupled with 1-naphthol to form an orange colored azo dye in alkaline medium. The size and shape effect of silver and gold nanoparticles in the time for diazotization is thus studied. The important analytical parameters and optimum reaction conditions have been evaluated.

Keywords : Silver and gold nanoparticles, diazotization, catalytic activity.

Introduction

Methyl parathion is one of the most hazardous insecticides that are used for the control of sucking and chewing insects in a very wide range of crops such as cereals, fruits, vegetables and cotton, and ornamentals¹. It is also known as Alkron, Niram, Rhodiatox, Thiophos, E-605, 3422, and SNP. It is highly toxic to nearly all forms of life makes it extremely valuable as insecticide and acaricide for controlling aphides, mites etc.²⁻⁵. Parathion residues are found in a variety of vegetable and foliage samples, which is causing great concern to national and international health authorities. The residual life of parathion on the plant surface was reported to be 5–12 days. Parathion has a high mammalian toxicity with an acute oral LD₅₀ to rats which varies from 5–15 mg/kg. A pesticide tolerance of 1 ppm (by weight) has been established by the Food and Drug Administration, USA⁶. It is reported to be mutagenic as well as teratogenic compound^{7,8}. It is reported to be excreted in the urine as *p*-nitrophenol. There have been many epidemics of poisoning by parathion in foods. The most common reaction mechanism evolved by microorganism to degrade parathion is the hydrolysis process through esterases⁹. The presence of reductive degradation systems among the micro-organisms is, however quiet apparent. For instance, the major degradation route

for parathion is the formation of amino parathion by reducing agents. Parathion is highly toxic in human body because it inactivates an essential enzyme called acetyl cholinesterase (ACHE). This enzyme functions in the body by destroying the biochemical acetylcholine, a substance that is stored in small cavities within certain type of cells of the nervous system called neurons. Acetylcholine is responsible for the transmission of nerve impulses from one neuron to another. The major medical problems by its misuses are respiratory failure, brain damage, gastric pain and salivation, etc. Due to the well known toxicity and wide usage of parathion, it is very important to determine its concentration in ppm level in plant materials and other environmental samples. A number of analytical methods, including gas chromatography mass spectroscopy (GC-MS)¹⁰, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)¹¹, electrochemical¹², spectrophotometric¹³ and Fourier transform (FT) Raman methods^{14,15} have been reported for this use. During the past few decades many results have been published in the area of spectrophotometric determination of parathion. The most common technique for the determination of parathion is spectrophotometry that is based on the reduction of nitro group present in parathion to amino group, which is subsequently diazotized and coupled with suitable reagent to give col-

ored product or by colorimetric determination of *p*-nitrophenol after alkaline hydrolysis of parathion. Some of the spectrophotometric methods are also based on the enzymatic inhibitory efficiency of parathion.

In this paper we present an alternative method, reducing the diazotization time by using conventional spectrophotometric method using 1-naphthol as a coupling reagent in presence of silver and gold nanoparticles for the determination of parathion. The method is based on the reduction of the nitro group of parathion to amino group (Scheme 1) which is subsequently diazotized in presence of silver and gold nanoparticles and coupled with 1-naphthol to form an azo dye in alkaline medium. The dye shows absorbance maxima at 500 nm. The azo dye is found to be stable for more than 30 h. The important analytical parameters like effect of reagents, time etc. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of parathion in fruit and soil sample.

Results and discussion

The dye formed in the proposed reaction shows maximum absorption at 500 nm (Fig. 1). The color system obeys Beer's law in the range of 10.0–83 μg of parathion in 25 ml of final volume (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of the azo dye formed in the proposed reaction (Given : concentration of parathion : 10 $\mu\text{g}/25$ ml).

Fig. 2. Calibration data for the determination of parathion (Beer's law).

The reduction of the nitro group of parathion to amino group was studied at different acidity. It was observed that constant absorbance values were obtained over the acidity range 0.2–5.0 *M* hydrochloric acid (Fig. 3a). At least 1 g of zinc dust and 2 ml of 5 *M* HCl were required for complete reduction. It was observed that 1 ml of sodium nitrite (Fig. 3b) and 2 ml of 1-naphthol was needed for full color development (Fig. 3c). The effect of diazotization time was studied and it was found that minimum 10 min was required for complete diazotization (Fig. 4a) but on adding silver (Fig. 4b) and gold (Fig. 4c) nanoparticles during diazotization it was found that the diazotization time was reduced to 5 min and 8 min respectively. Figs. 5a and 5b shows the TEM photographs

Fig. 3(a). Effect of acidity (conc. of HCl) on the process of diazotization (Given : parathion concentration = 10 μ g/25 ml).

Fig. 3(b). Effect of amount of sodium nitrite on the process of diazotization (Given : parathion concentration = 10 μ g/25 ml).

Fig. 3(c). Effect of amount of 1-naphthol on the process of diazotization (Given : parathion concentration = 10 μ g/25 ml).

of silver and gold nanoparticles respectively. It clearly shows that most of the silver nanoparticles are in triangular

Fig. 4(a). Effect of time for diazotization without using nanoparticles; a = 5 min; b = 10 min.

Fig. 4(b). Effect of time for diazotization using silver nanoparticles; a = 5 min; b = 10 min.

Fig. 4(c). Effect of time for diazotization using gold nanoparticles; a = 5 min; b = 10 min.

lar shape whereas gold nanoparticles are almost spherical.

Fig. 5(a). TEM image of silver nanoparticle sample prepared in sodium citrate (microwave conditions : 300 W, irradiated for 3 min, inset showed a single silver nanoprism with spherical nanoparticles).

Fig. 5(b). TEM image of gold nanoparticle sample prepared in sodium citrate (microwave conditions : 300 W, irradiated for 3 min).

Experimental

Instrumentation :

- UV-Visible spectra were recorded with Carl Zeiss Jena Spekol fitted with an EK-5 unit and matched glass cells of 1-cm optical path length.
- Variable volume (10–100 μL) micropipette, Glaxosmithline Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Finland was used for handling liquid volumes.
- Sartorius electronic balance, AG Göttingen Germany, Model CP225D (Precision 10 μg) was used for weighing measurements.

Chemicals :

Parathion solution (10 $\mu\text{g}/25\text{ ml}$), hydrochloric acid (5 M), zinc dust, sodium nitrite (0.25%), sulphamic acid (3%), EDTA (0.1), 1-naphthol (0.2%), sodium hydroxide (5 M). All reagents used were of analytical grade (BDH/Merck).

Procedure :

An aliquot of standard solution containing 10–83 μg of parathion was taken in a test tube and to it $\sim 1\text{ g}$ of zinc dust and 2 ml of 5 M hydrochloric acid were added.

Then 1 ml of sodium nitrite and nanoparticles were added and the solution was kept for 10 min for complete diazotization. 1 ml of sulphamic acid was added to remove excess of sodium nitrite. Finally 2 ml of 1-naphthol was added and kept for 3 min for coupling. The solution was then made alkaline with sodium hydroxide to produce an azo dye (Scheme 2). The absorbance of this dye was measured at 500 nm against reagent blank.

Scheme 2. The color reaction.

Application :

The application of this method was done with fruit, vegetable and soil sample as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Determination of parathion in various plant material and soil

Samples	Parathion added ($\mu\text{g}/25\text{ ml}$)	Total parathion Found ($\mu\text{g}/25\text{ ml}$)	Difference ($\mu\text{g}/25\text{ ml}$)	Recovery (%)
Tomato ^a	10	19.5	9.5	95
	20	40.5	20.5	103
Apple ^a	10	19.0	9.0	90
	20	39.5	19.5	98
Soil ^a	10	20.5	10.5	105
	20	38.5	18.5	93

^aAmount of sample : 25 g.

Conclusion

The proposed method is rapid, simple and sensitive and the reagent described here is sensitive and selective for parathion insecticides containing a nitro group. It can be precisely determined down to 0.4 ppm. The problem with low sensitivity and more time is resolved by the adsorption of parathion pesticides onto silver and gold nanoparticles during diazotization process. The catalytic activity of metal nanoparticles depends on their size and shape^{16,17}. A change in electronic properties, a high surface to volume ratio, and an increase in numbers of edges, corners and faces contribute to the enhancement in activity and selectivity of nanoparticles, so it can be concluded that the relatively better result observed with silver nanoparticles in this work may be due to availability of triangular shape particles, as the shape variation, together with the increased number of edges, corners and faces, is of critical importance in controlling the catalytic activity and selectivity of metal nanoparticles¹⁸. The increased number of corners and edges increases the surface area and that increased surface area of nanoparticles acts as a substrate for the various chemical reaction¹⁹⁻²¹. The present method shows the reduction of diazotization timing by using nanoparticles, fast process due to catalytic activity of nanoparticles and low detection limit. The application of this method in the determination of parathion in fruit and soil sample demonstrated the usefulness of the method for its determination at low levels.

References

1. M. C. Pablos Espada, F. J. Arrebola-Liebnas, A. Garrido-Frenich and J. L. Martinez-Vidal, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1999, **75**, 165.
2. R. W. Stevens and M. Dekker, "Pesticides in the Environment", Vol. 1, New York, 1976.
3. H. Martin, "Pesticides Manual", British Crop Protection Council, 335, London, 1968.
4. T. F. West and J. E. Hardy, "Chemical Control of Insects", Vol. 105, Chapman & Hall Ltd., London, 1961.
5. F. A. Gunther and J. D. Gunther, "Residue Reviews", Vol. 45, Springer Verlag, New York, 1973.
6. F. A. Patty, "Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology", Interscience Publishers, London, 1962.
7. E. S. Samuel and M. Legator, "The Mutagenicity of Pesticides", The MIT Press, Cambridge, 1971.
8. E. J. Calabrese, "Pollutants and High Risk Groups", Wiley-Interscience Publication, New York, 1978.
9. C. A. Edwards, "Environmental Pollution by Pesticides", Plenum Press, London, 1973.
10. J. E. Patsias and J. Papadopoulou-Mourkidou, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 1996, **83**, 740.
11. C. Goncalves and M. F. Alpendurada, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2004, **1026**, 239.
12. E. Papadopoulou-Mourkidou and J. J. Patsias, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 1996, **99**, 726.
13. L. Hart, W. A. Collier and D. Janssen, *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 1997, **12**, 645.
14. S. G. Skoulika and C. A. Georgiou, *Appl. Spectrosc.*, 2000, **54**, 747.
15. M. Alak-Ala and T. Vo-Dinh, *Anal. Chem.*, 1987, **59**, 2149.
16. S. Chen, K. Huang and J. A. Stearns, *Chem. Mater.*, 2000, **12**, 540.
17. C. M. Shen, Y. K. Su, H. T. Yang, T. Z. Yang and H. G. Gao, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2003, **373**, 39.
18. T. S. Ahmadi, Z. L. Wang, T. C. Green, A. Henglein and M. A. El-Sayed, *Science*, 1996, **272**, 1924.
19. G. H. Wang, W. C. Li, K. M. Jia, B. Spliethoff, F. Schuth and A. H. Lu, *Applied Catalysis A : General*, 2009, **364**, 42.
20. X. Gong, Y. Yang, L. Zhang, C. Zou, P. Cai and G. Chen, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2010, **352**, 379.
21. J. Park, P. K. Karandikar, K. Jun and H. G. Park, *Applied Catalysis A : General*, 2012, 411.

